

Images of Women in *Time to be Happy* by Nayantara Sahgal

by **T. Saheeda Begum**, *Guest Lecturer,*
Department of Humanities,

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Institute of Technology, Port Blair - 744103

&

Naw Jennifer, *Guest Lecturer,*
Department of English,

M.G. Govt. College, Mayabunder - 744204

Introduction :

Nayantara Sahgal (1927), one of the leading contemporary Indian English writers, has been writing for more than four decades now. She is a prolific writer and has written not only nine novels but also autobiographies, political commentaries and a large number of essays on contemporary issues of national importance. In the prime of her life she wrote regularly for newspapers and magazines and has contributed a large number of articles to it. She is the foremost political novelist in India.

Being the daughter of Vijayalakshmi Pandit and niece of Jawaharlal Nehru, Nayantara Sahgal naturally had an upbringing in which politics was inevitably a strong ambience. She imbibed political ideology from her environment which proved a rich source of material for her novels. This is what made Nayantara Sahgal an exponent of the political novel. She has herself declared that each of her novels 'more or less reflects the political era the audiences are passing through.

Nayantara Sahgal has written nine novels. Sahgal's first novel, *A Time to be Happy*, appeared in 1958 and then came *This Time of Morning* (1965), *Storm in*

Chandigarh (1969), *The Day in Shadow* (1971), *A Situation in New Delhi* (1977), *Rich Like us* (1985), *Plans for Departure* (1986) and *Mistaken Identity* (1988). Her last novel, *Lesser Breeds* came in 2003. Each of her novels chronicles the socio-political development of India just before and after the independence of the country from the British rule. Most of her novels are woven round some important political event. Interestingly, as compared to other eminent Indian English novelists, Kamala Markandaya has chosen a larger canvas and variegated life of the Indian people. It is evident that Markandaya depicts the theme of hunger and degradation in the context of poor farmers, prostitutes, unemployed youth and ladies in pursuit of modernity whereas most of the Indian England writers have depicted this theme in the context of downtrodden section of society only. Kamala Markandaya does not follow any 'ism'. Rather she is an independent observer of life and she does not mould her story under the influence of any 'ism' or any philosophical or political commitment.

Nayantara Sahgal stands for humanism, Woman, to her, is not a mere toy, an object of lust, but man's equal and honoured partner in word and deed, as against the inhuman, traditional pastures, "Old impossible ideas," taboos and prejudices which, being out of date, must be cast aside like old clothes. Sahgal's women refuse to fit into the mould of "perfect angel." They show their hesitation in a decent and gentle way. M.L. Mahotra says that "Sahgal's women characters have only one passion: "It is the longing to be free, freedom from all restraint in word and deed being their monomania. They want to be fully alive and themselves"

My mother, though inwardly shocked by his refusal, had staunchly supported him against criticism, as she supported all his views and enterprises against the displeasures, I am sure of gods. It was for her husband, she felt, to right his actions in the eyes of God Like any good Hindu wife she believed that his concern was with God and hers with God in him (A Time to Be Happy 5).

Her happiness comes not from satisfactory circumstances of life but from her acceptance of it. She has made up her mind to be happy for anything which makes her mind to be happy. She strongly believes that she has no separate desires, tastes, likings or ambitions in life. Her only ambition in life is to live up to the expectations of her husband and make everyone happy both inside and outside home. She is selfless in all means and as a result she achieves perfect harmony with her husband. She finds happiness within the confines of Hindu orthodoxy. It is because

of her total acceptance of traditional injustice. While describing the marital harmony of his parents the narrator says:

“In spite of their disagreements, and there must have been some in a marriage that lasted fifty years ... one might say they were compelled to maintain it, because marriage, among us, is for life, and those who do not adjust to its ups and downs must forever remain unhappy” (A Time to Be Happy 6).

She is presenting the picture of a conventional, ‘family lady’. She is the type of a ‘dream girl’ that every young man of the male dominated Indian society wants for his life. One cannot expect all the women will have the qualities of the narrator’s mother. She is a very rare find and in this modern world it is impossible to get such characters: Govind Narayan’s mother, though she belongs to the same generation as that of the narrator’s mother, does not see any match between the views of her husband and those of hers. She maintains her individuality though she could not influence her husband’s mind. The narrator observes:

“The indolent, pleasure loving man who had married her and brought her here had not understood her mun-like disdain of luxury, her stubborn refusal to submit to the mould in which he had tried to cast her (A Time to Be Happy 25).

This woman, though she belongs to the older generation, has a strong will power to maintain her actual personality. Sahgal describes her:

“She had, in her youth, been a woman of character at a time when character was not admired in women of breeding and later this had given way to a sharp criticism of all that she disapproved of in her husband and his home”(A Time to Be Happy 25).

Her husband, like the most of the men of that age, never tries to understand her emotions, desires and hopes. Instead, he cleverly avoids situations which would create chances for any argument. Finally she compromises herself with her lot, becomes passive like a typical Indian woman and this saves their marital bond from any possible damage. “All my needs are here within the house’, she declared. “What is there for me in the world outside? You who are young must enjoy yourselves. For me the worldly life is over and the time of contemplation begun” (A Time to Be

Happy 29). Here, Sahgal seems to suggest that the marital disharmony can be avoided if the partners show readiness to bend by having compromises rather than breaking the relationship by adopting rigid attitudes.

Maya Shivpal is one of the protagonists of the story. She is the first character of Sahgal who starts the journey towards self-realization. Maya has enjoyed a rich and happy background with her parents before marriage. Her presence has been very much enjoyed by the family members. Her individual interests and wishes have been honoured at home. But her marriage with Harish has changed everything upside down. Her marriage is doomed right from the beginning. Sahgal shows great sympathy for women who are married into backgrounds different from their own. They need time and understanding from their husbands at least, to adjust to their new atmosphere, but they rarely get these comforts. She is a woman with full of ambitions and aspirations. Her dreams of self determination and self realization take her to rural India. She has a natural instinct towards social work and she feels very much contented with her service in the villages.

Lakshmi, Govind Narayan's wife, is another woman who is fully contented as a wife and mother. She is not interested in maintaining her individual identity and she expects other women also like her. When Maya experiences psychological troubles with her husband, Lakshmi, a member of Harish family, does not show any sympathy for Maya. She does not understand Maya's aspiration and is rather irritated at her behaviour. She comments:

“Maya wants to work in a village ... It's not a laughing matter ... Don't you think it is tactless of her? It's embarrassing for Harish with her getting mixed up in the congress programme. Why can't she join a music circle or a literary society or something he'll approve of” (A Time to Be Happy 32).

Lakshmi believes that the existence of a wife must necessarily be subordinate to that of her husband. If she does not encourage her husband in his pursuits, she must be crazy. Sahgal points out women like Lakshmi join hands with men in oppressing their own kind. It is not malice but their ignorance that motivates them to work against the 'new woman.' Lakshmi never tries to understand the feelings of Maya and she criticizes her without any sympathy.

Conclusion :

Through the woman characters Maya and Kusum in “*A Time to be Happy*” Sahgal has tried to bring out the struggle in the marital bondage. Before her marriage to Harish, Maya enjoyed a rich and happy background but her marriage with Harish has changed everything upside down. She is like a fish out of water in the world of her husband. Her dreams of self-determination and self realization take her to rural India. Kusum who is married to Sanad also struggles in her marital bondage. She has no interest and she does not want to get into world of Sanad, but for the sake of maintaining marital harmony, she is forced to change herself to the level of attending clubs, wearing high heels and drinking cocktails. She is able to save her marital relationship as she has learnt to be accommodative.

Lakshmi, who is another woman character in this novel, is full contented as a wife and mother. She firmly believes that the existence of a wife must necessarily be subordinate to that of her husband. Sahgal goes on to say that women like Lakshmi join hands with men in oppressing their own kind.

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